

KNOWLEDGE OF MOTHERS ON POSTNATAL CARE

Mrs. Bananee Dash¹, Dr. Darshan Sohi², Dr. Manjubala Dash³

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: The health of women actually represents the health of the country she comes from. Women are the primary care taker, first education, bearers and nurtures of the next generation. Safe motherhood can only be reached if complete care is given to mothers. It is the comprehensive or total care that can be offered to women. **Objective:** To assess the knowledge of the mothers regarding postnatal care **Methodology:** The research approach was quantitative and design was descriptive design. Total 35 mothers were selected with purposive sampling technique. **Result:** The result shows that with regards to distribution of age of primi mother 3 (8.57%) are coming under 22-23 years,. The mean knowledge level of mothers regarding postnatal care. Result showed that mothers mean knowledge level was 10.57 with standard deviation of 2 regarding postnatal care. **Conclusion:** Postnatal Mothers had inadequate knowledge regarding postnatal care. Hence education programmes are necessary to educate the mothers regarding postnatal care.

Keywords: Knowledge, Mothers, Postnatal care

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INTRODUCTION:

Motherhood is a beautiful experience where by the mother safely delivers a child. it is the magic of creation. care must be given to ensure safe child birth. the mother has a right to get proper medical care and treatment. labor is a natural process, which all pregnant women have to undergo [1-2]. The mother experiences physiological changes as per body regain its non-pregnant state and psychological changes as she adjusts herself to the new face of motherhood with a separate but a depended infant [3-5]. It has been stated that the postnatal care is related to the needs of each individual mother rather than to any routine pattern. Emphasis should be given according to the need of the individual mother [6-9]. The post-partum period or puerperium (from the Latin pure, "child" and par ere "to bring forth") refer to the six-week period after child birth [1-12].

OBJECTIVE

- To assess the knowledge of the mothers regarding postnatal care
- To associate the level of knowledge with selected variables.

METHODOLOGY

The research approach was quantitative and design was descriptive design. Total 35 mothers were selected with purposive sampling technique, those who had normal vaginal delivery and willing to participate in the study were interviewed with the structured interview schedule. The study was conducted in the selected village of Odisha [13-15].

RESULT AND FINDINGS

The result shows that with regards to distribution of age of primi mother 3 (8.57%) are coming under 22-23 years, 27 (77.15%) coming under 24-25 years and remaining 5 (14.28%) coming under 26-27 years. Regarding the education of mothers out of 35, 6 (17.15%) have education up to secondary level, 15(42.85%) have education up to higher secondary level, 12 (34.28%) have education up to graduate and the remaining 2 (5.72%) are post graduate. With regard to employment 5 mothers (14.27%) are working as teachers and mill workers, where the remaining 30 (85.73%) are unemployed. Regarding monthly family income 9 (25.72%) had an income below ₹. 4000 per month, 15 (42.85%) earns between ₹. 4001 - ₹. 7000 and 11(31.43%) earns more than ₹. 7000 per month. Regarding religion all the primi mothers 35 (100%) belong to Hindu religion. Regarding the type of family 17 mothers (48.57%) lives in rural area and the rest 18 (51.43%) lives in urban area. Regarding the area of living 25 mothers (71.43%) lives in nuclear family and the rest 10 (28.57%) lives in joint family. Regarding postnatal care 22 (62.85%) mothers obtained information from relatives and friends, 8 (22.85 %) from neighbours and remaining 5 (14.28%) from health personnels. (Tab-1)

Tab-1- Distribution of demographic variable of the Postnatal mothers. N=35

S. No.	Demographic Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age		
	a) 22-23 years	3	8.57
	b) 24-25 years	27	77.15
	c) 26-27 years	5	14.28
2.	Educational status		
	a) Secondary	6	17.15
	b) Higher Secondary	15	42.85
	c) Graduate	12	34.28
	d) Post graduate	2	5.72

3.	Occupation of mother		
	a) Employed	5	14.27
	b) Unemployed	30	85.73
4.	Monthly family income		
	a) Below ₹. 4000	9	25.72
	b) ₹. 4001 - ₹. 7000	15	42.85
	c) ₹. 7000 and above	11	31.43
5.	Religion		
	a) Hindu	35	100
	b) Muslim	0	0
	c) Christian	0	0
6.	Type of Family		
	a) Nuclear family	17	48.57
	b) Joint family	18	51.43
7.	Area of living		
	a) Rural	25	71.43
	b) Urban	10	28.57
8.	Sources of information regarding postnatal care		
	a) Relatives and friends	22	62.85
	b) Neighbours	8	22.85
	c) Health personnels	5	14.30

Table (2) shows the mean knowledge level of mothers regarding postnatal care. Result showed that mothers mean knowledge level was 10.57 with standard deviation of 2 regarding postnatal care.

Tab2- Distribution of level of knowledge among Postnatal Mothers

Variable	Mean	S.D
Knowledge	10.57	2.0

CONCLUSION

Postnatal mothers had inadequate knowledge in various aspects of postnatal care. Hence there must be various programmes to create awareness among these mothers.

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